

A Study of Achievement Motivation in Relation to Locality and Academic Stream of Senior Secondary School Students of Bareilly District

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigated the achievement motivation of senior secondary school students in relation to their locality and academic stream. A total of 200 students comprised of 100 rural (50 Science & 50 commerce) and 100 urban (50 Science & 50 commerce) students selected randomly from ten senior secondary schools of Bareilly district. Achievement Motivation Test (Ach.MT) developed by Dr. V.P. Bhargava (2009) was administered on the sample to assess the achievement motivation. Two way ANOVA was used to analyse the data. The results revealed that locality and academic stream of students had highly significant effect on achievement motivation, but there was no significant interaction effect of locality and academic stream on achievement motivation of senior secondary school students.

KEYWORDS: Achievement motivation, Locality, Academic stream, senior secondary school students.

INTRODUCTION

Achievement motivation, a vital force for secondary school students, is the internal spark that propels individuals toward success. For pursuit of excellence in the dynamic landscape of secondary education, this intrinsic drive becomes a guiding light. Beyond the quest for good grades, achievement motivation encompasses a broader commitment to personal growth and the attainment of meaningful goals.

In the classroom, this motivation fuels curiosity, encouraging to actively engage in learning and strive for academic excellence. It extends beyond textbooks, influencing involvement in extracurricular activities, sports, and creative pursuits. Embracing achievement motivation empowers, it set ambitious yet achievable goals, fostering resilience in the face of challenges.

McClelland *et al.* (1959) defined achievement motivation as a competition with a standard of excellence. Thus the achievement motivation is characterized by a desire to attain a high standard of excellence and to accomplish the unique objective. The self-imposed requirement for good performance or accomplishment of some unique work may be called as need to accomplish something worthwhile, unique or excellent or need for mastery. The achievement motive drives an individual to strive to gain mastery of difficult and challenging situation. It comes into the picture when an individual knows that his performance will be evaluated, that the consequence of his actions will lead either to success or failure and that good performance will produce a feeling of pride in accomplishment. The achievement motive may thus be considered to be a disposition to approach success or the capacity to take pride in

accomplishment when success is achieved in an activity. As for the original and development of the achievement motive, it can be safely said that it is conditioned by one's early training, experiences and subsequent learning. In general, children usually acquire the achievement motive from their parent's lifestyle. Studies have shown that the children whose independent training starts at an early age and who get more autonomy within a cooperative, encouraging and less authoritarian and healthy home environment usually develop an achievement oriented attitude. Later, on the experiences and learning based on the circumstances and situations in his life may lead an individual to provide a level for the intensity of his achievement motive to struggle for attaining the standard of excellence desired by him.

Spinatha *et al.* (2006) suggested that level of achievement motivation is based on emotions and achievement related goals. Students with high achievement goals study hard and definitely persist longer when they approach difficulties whereas low achievement goals students perform worse at learning task, tend to avoid difficult task, and do not really regulate their learning behavior.

Achievement motivation is the basic need for success or the attainment of excellence. Achievement motivation can be understood simply as the tendency to strive for success or the attainment of a desired goal. The importance of achievement motivation in the learning and achievement process has been given a great goal of attention in the recent researches. Individuals will satisfy their needs through different means, and are driven to succeed for varying reasons both internal and external. According to McClelland (1985), Achievement motivation has been defined as the extent to which individuals differ in their need to strive to attain rewards, such as physical satisfaction, praise from others and feelings of personal mastery (Singh, B. & Sagar, P., 2019).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Meijer *et al.* (2004); Awan *et al.* (2011) and Emmanuel *et al.* (2014) investigated that achievement motivation is significantly related with academic achievement. Chetri (2014) found a positive significantly correlation between achievement motivation and academic achievement. Pany, S. (2014); Shekhar, C. & Choudhary, P. (2017); Rani, P. & Reddy, R. G. (2019) reveals that achievement motivation of science stream students is significantly differ from arts stream students, whereas Chiramel, V. T. & Vasuki, N. (2018); Roy, S. & Saha (2022) found a non significant difference between science and arts stream students on achievement motivation. Singh, R. (2019) investigated a non significant difference between science and commerce steam students on achievement motivation. Velmugugan, K. & BalaKrishnan, V. (2013); Ansary, K., Saha, B. & Gorain, S. C. (2021); Roy, S. & Saha, B. (2022) investigated a non significant difference between rural and urban school students on achievement motivation. While, Pany, S. (2014); Shekhar, C. & Choudhary, P. (2017) found that rural area students are significantly differ from urban area students on achievement motivation. Chiramel, V. T. & Vasuki, N. (2018) investigated a non significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees from rural and urban areas.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Achievement Motivation provides a means of powerful and higher aim in the life of the students. As a human concept, Achievement Motivation involves creativity in the discovery of patterns of learning and reaching the goal. Therefore, it is one of the essential areas of learning. Everyone needs to develop Achievement Motivational concepts and skills; this would help them to understand and motivate in learning that would also help them to achieve their goal. In education achievement motivation aims to provide students understanding with their right motive to achieve the right goal.

According to the quoted research review, the achievement motivation plays an important role in predicting students' future success. Therefore, it is crucial to put special emphasis on forming high level of students' need for achievement through special training programs and proper guidance. Achievement motivation is one of the crucial psychological factors determining future academic and occupational success. At the secondary level students should be selected the stream and subjects of their own interest and capacity. The researcher feels that this study will highlight the role of achievement motivation for one's life.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the differences on achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students.
2. To find out the differences on achievement motivation of science and commerce stream students.
3. To study the interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation of senior secondary school students.

HYPOTHESIS

- H1.** There is no significant difference on achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students.
- H2.** There is no significant difference on achievement motivation of science and commerce stream students.
- H3.** There is no significant interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation of senior secondary school students.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research method has been adopted for this study. The population for the study comprised all senior secondary school students of Bareilly district affiliated to UP board. A sample of 200 students comprised of 100 rural (50 Science & 50 commerce) and 100 urban (50 Science & 50 commerce) students selected randomly from ten senior secondary schools. Achievement motivation test developed by Dr. V.P. Bhargava (2009) was administered to assess the level of achievement motivation. Two way ANOVA was used to analyse the data collected from the sample. The present study was delimited to science and commerce stream students of Bareilly district affiliated to UP board only.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The analysis of the data, interpretation and discussion of the findings are presented below:

Table-1: Descriptive Statistics of Achievement motivation

	Locality	Academic stream	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Achievement	Rural	Science	23.48	3.27	50
		Commerce	17.82	4.14	50
		Total	20.65	4.68	100

Motivation	Urban	Science	26.24	3.86	50
		Commerce	19.50	3.52	50
Total		22.87	5.00	100	
Total	Total	Science	24.86	3.82	100
		Commerce	18.66	3.91	100
		Total	21.76	4.95	200

(1) Analysis of main effect of locality, academic stream of students and their interaction on achievement motivation.

Table-2: Summary of Analysis of Variance of Achievement Motivation

Sources of Variance	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F- Ratio
Locality	1	246.42	246.42	17.89**
Academic stream	1	1922.00	1922.00	139.55**
Locality*Academic stream	1	14.58	14.58	1.06
Error	196	2699.48	13.77	

**Significant at 0.01 Significance level

H1. There is no significant difference on achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students.

From table-2, it is revealed that F-value (17.89) for main effect of locality on achievement motivation is found to be highly significant at 0.01 level of significance for df (1,196). It denotes that locality of students affect their achievement motivation significantly. So, null hypothesis (H₁) that 'there is no significant difference on achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students' is rejected and it can be inferred that the achievement motivation of rural and urban area students differ significantly. As per fig.1 findings, urban students were more motivated (M=22.87) as compared to rural students (M=20.65). The study revealed that urban students have more consciousness to their future success.

Similar results have been reported by Pany, S. (2014) and Shekhar, C. & Choudhary, P. (2017) found a significant effect of locality on achievement motivation. Although, there are few research studies which did not support the present results, like- Kaur & Meenu (2013); Velmugugan, K. & Balakrishanan, V. (2013); Ansary, K. *et al.* (2021) and Roy, S. & Saha (2022). They found a non significant difference on achievement motivation of rural and urban area students.

Fig.1. Achievement motivation of rural and urban senior secondary school students

H2. There is no significant difference on achievement motivation of science and commerce stream students.

As per table -2, F value (139.55) is found to be highly significant at 0.01 significance level for df (1,196) for main effect of academic stream on achievement motivation. So assertion made by null hypothesis (H.2) that 'there is no significant difference on achievement motivation of science and commerce stream students' is rejected. It refers that academic stream affect the achievement motivation of students significantly. It is observed from fig.2, that science stream students (M=24.86) had high level of achievement motivation as compared to commerce steam students (M=18.66).

The results of present study is supported by Pany, S. (2014); Shekhar, C. & Choudhary, P. (2017) and Rani, P. & Reddy, R.G. (2019) found a significant effect of academic stream on achievement motivation. Whereas, there are few studies which did not favour the present findings, like - Chiramel, V.T. & Vasuki, N. (2018); Singh, R. (2019) and Roy, S. & Saha (2022) found a non significant effect of academic stream on achievement motivation.

Fig. 2. Achievement motivation of Science and Commerce stream students

H3. There is no significant interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation of senior secondary school students.

From table -2, F-value (1.06) is found to be non significant at 0.01 significance level for df (1,196) for interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation. Hence, null hypothesis (H3) that 'there is no significant interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation of senior secondary school students.' is accepted.

Fig.3: Locality & Stream wise Graphical Representation of Mean & Standard Deviation

The fact, F-value for the interaction between locality and academic stream of students is not found significant. It indicates that the achievement motivation of science and commerce stream students of the rural and urban area do not differ significantly from another. With a non significant interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation, It may be said that main effect due to locality i.e., significant difference among the mean scores of achievement motivation for rural and urban students, is independent of the effect of academic stream of students.

Fig.4. Interaction between Locality and Academic stream on achievement motivation

SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

The following was the main findings of the study-

1. Locality of the students affects their achievement motivation.
2. Academic stream also affect the achievement motivation of the students.
3. The interaction effect between locality and academic stream on achievement motivation to be not significant.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that locality affect the achievement motivation of students significantly. Urban area students reported higher level of achievement motivation compared to their rural counterparts. Science stream students reported higher level of achievement motivation compared to commerce stream students. It means science stream students have high motivation to accomplish valued goals and to avoid failure. It is also concluded that interaction between locality and academic stream did not affect the achievement motivation of students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Many studies are concerned that high academic achievement is positively correlated with future success of students and academic achievement increases with the increase in achievement motivation. At

the senior secondary level students should select the streams and subjects of their own interest and capacities. Academic counselors should organize guidance programs such as workshops, symposia and public lectures periodically for students to equip them to enhance their academic performance and achievement motivation. Quiz competitions, co-curricular activities, class presentations and inter school debates should be organized that can motivate the students to improve their academic performance. A wide variety of teaching methods should be used in the classroom to increase the achievement motivation of students.

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